

Fighting Sleep an Ideal Way Without Coffee

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Abstract: *These macronutrients help the body absorb nutrients that help it absorb.*

Keywords: *protein products and slow carbohydrates, phosphorus, gives a burst of energy, increases alertness, improves attention and reduces the level of cortisol, the stress hormone.*

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How to perk up without coffee?

Try alternative drinks

According to a sports doctor, coffee can be replaced with matcha tea: the phosphorus and honey it contains increase concentration and improve mood. Herbal tea with ginger and lemon is another good alternative. The drink tones, contains vitamins C, B2, B1, and has an immunostimulating effect.

Take a walk

Fresh air and physical activity will help you perk up quickly. As soon as you start to feel sleepy, close your laptop and go for a walk - you don't have to run in circles, just take a short walk down the street. Research shows that this invigorates you better than coffee

Don't skip breakfast

To maintain energy for the whole day, breakfast should be complete - not just a cup of coffee with cookies. Include protein products and slow carbohydrates (for example, cottage cheese or fish, cereals) in your morning meal - in this case, you will have enough strength until the evening. But fast carbohydrates that instantly increase blood sugar levels are not a good idea. The risk of falling asleep right on your desk after lunch increases in this case. By the way, a heavy lunch can also provoke a loss of strength and a desire to take a nap.

Warm up

To start working with renewed energy, it is enough to move a little. Scientists compared those who drink caffeine and those who engage in physical activity (for example, walking). The latter turned out to be more energetic. So take note: any, even a small, activity gives a surge of energy.

Chew gum

Scientists have proven that chewing gum is beneficial: it gives a burst of energy, increases alertness, improves attention and reduces the level of cortisol, the stress hormone. Choose fruity and minty flavors - volunteers who took part in an experiment with chewing gum noted an improvement in mood. It's worth a try - at least your breath will be fresh.

How to wake up quickly: eight simple tips

Don't reset the alarm clock If the alarm goes off, get out from under the covers. ...

Drink water A glass of water in the morning will help you wake up and drive away drowsiness. ...

Turn on the light ...

Breathe deeply ...

Massage the right points ...

Do exercises ...

Take a contrast shower ...

Eat breakfast

How to overcome the desire to sleep?

Do light exercises, periodically get up from your workplace to stretch. Rub your earlobes and palms, there are many biologically active points there. Massage your head, comb your hair - this will improve blood circulation. Drink a cup of coffee - caffeine stimulates the nervous system.

9 ways to perk up when you haven't had enough sleep

Have breakfast right away Lack of sleep disrupts the normal feeling of hunger. ...

Take a walk in the sun ...

Be more active ...

Breathe deeply ...

Cool down ...

Try not to lie down "for a little nap" ...

Drink more water ...

Avoid using electronic devices in the evening

How to fall asleep quickly and not wake up at night?

Secrets of sound and healthy sleep

Sleep routine

Reduce your overall need for sleep

Keep a sleep journal

Avoid daytime naps

Sleep in a cool room

Sleep in silence

Avoid bright colors in the bedroom

Use the right pillow

Use a sleep mask

Conclusion: try alternative drinks take a walk don't skip breakfast stretch your legs chew gum.

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